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Providing a common base for life cycle assessments of Li-Ion batteriesJens F. Peters¹, Marcel Weil^{1,2}¹ Helmholtz Institute Ulm (HIU), Helmholtzstr. 11, 89081 Ulm (Germany)³² ITAS, Institute for Technology Assessment and Systems Analysis, Karlsruhe (Germany)³³ Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), P.O. Box 3640, 76021 Karlsruhe, Germany**Abstract**

Numerous studies exist on the environmental impact of Li-Ion battery (LIB) production. Nevertheless, these studies use different impact assessment methods and different approaches for modelling key aspects like energy demand for cell manufacturing or the composition of the cell package. Since the outcomes of the studies are highly sensitive on these aspects, a direct comparison of the corresponding results is not possible. However, a robust comparative analysis would be of high interest for evaluating the actual environmental performance of different alternative battery chemistries. Based on a review of existing LCA studies on LIB production, the corresponding discrepancies in the modelling of these key aspects are pointed out and their impact on the outcomes of the underlying studies is highlighted. The existing primary life cycle inventory data (LCI) for the principle LIB chemistries are then recompiled and common average values implemented for the identified key parameters. In this way, the environmental impacts associated with the production of different battery chemistries are assessed on a common base. This provides an improved comparability between studies and allows for a tentative technology benchmarking of different Li-Ion battery chemistries. It can be observed that the different assumptions and modelling approaches for the mentioned key aspects can have a stronger impact on the final results than the battery chemistry itself. Especially the approach for modelling the cell manufacturing energy demand, but also for the electrode binder and the battery management system influence the results significantly. Thus, putting existing LCA studies on a common base is essential for battery technology benchmarking and avoids erroneous conclusions when comparing the environmental impacts associated with the production of different Li-Ion battery chemistries.

30 **1 Introduction**

31 The decarbonisation of transport and mobility services is considered to be one of the keys for reducing
32 anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Under this framework, electric vehicles are being
33 promoted for achieving a transition towards renewable energies also in this sector and for reducing the
34 corresponding environmental impacts [2,3]. While the environmental impacts of electric mobility are
35 usually dominated by the use phase, the production of the battery also plays a significant role. This
36 becomes increasingly important when a higher share of renewable energy is used for charging [4–7]
37 and in this way the relevance of the use phase decreases. For electric vehicles, lithium-ion batteries
38 (LIB) have become the dominating battery technology, basically due to their high energy density and
39 their high charge-discharge efficiencies [8]. Numerous studies exist that quantify the impact of the
40 production process for different types of LIB along their lifetime [9]. For this purpose, life cycle
41 assessment (LCA) is commonly used, a standardized methodology for determining the environmental
42 impacts of products or services over their whole life cycle [5,10–13]. While the LCA process itself is
43 standardized, numerous assumptions and simplifications are necessary when modelling the assessed
44 products and processes, and different methodologies are available for quantifying the environmental
45 impacts. The existing LCA studies on LIB production are very heterogeneous in this regard, applying
46 different impact assessment methods, but also different approaches for modelling key components or
47 parameters of the assessed batteries [9]. However, these key parameters can have significant
48 influence on the outcomes of the studies. For example, the energy demand for cell manufacturing is a
49 major contributor to the GHG emissions associated with battery production, but varies up to an order
50 of magnitude between the different studies [9]. Also other aspects like the type of cell housing (pouch
51 cells or round cells), or the modelling of the battery management system (BMS) significantly affect the
52 mass balance of a battery module and thus the outcome of the corresponding LCA. Therefore, no
53 common basis for comparing the environmental performance of different alternative LIB chemistries
54 exists, while it seems very desirable to support decisions of technology developers. While this problem
55 has been pointed out by various authors previously, it has not yet been addressed [14–17]. This paper
56 presents a promising approach for unifying life cycle inventories (LCI) of existing LCA studies on LIB
57 production and thus for assessing LIB from different studies on a common base. This increases the
58 comparability of the results provided by these studies for different types of LIB significantly. The
59 outcomes also serve as reference for assessing or benchmarking novel battery chemistries against
60 existing LIB in an identical battery configuration.

61 **2 Methodology**

62 **2.1 Identification of discrepancies in existing inventory data**

63 The basis for this work is a previous review of existing life cycle assessment (LCA) studies of LIB [9].
64 In this review, the heterogeneity of published LCA studies was identified as one of the main hurdles
65 for a meaningful comparison of the results. In particular, different cell configurations are used and
66 some key components of LIB are modelled very differently (using different, more or less appropriate
67 proxies for certain chemicals and components), while for a sound comparison of different battery

68 chemistries, a common base would be highly recommended (e.g., same cell configuration, use of
 69 identical modelling approaches for common substances / components). For this purpose, all studies
 70 that transparently disclose the underlying life cycle inventories (LCI) and that use at least a significant
 71 share of own original data within the LCI are selected from the mentioned review. Five studies are
 72 identified that use exclusively own primary LCI and disclose the LCI data completely and sufficiently
 73 detailed for recompilation: Zackrisson et al. [18], Notter et al. [19], Bauer [20], Majeau-Bettez et al.
 74 [21] and Ellingsen et al. [14]. Five different LIB chemistries are covered by these studies: Lithium iron
 75 phosphate (LFP), manganese spinel oxide (LMO), composite oxides (NCM and NCA); all with graphite
 76 anodes, and lithium iron phosphate with lithium titanate anode (LTO).

77 The LCI of these studies are extracted as far as disclosed, recompiled and implemented in openLCA
 78 with as little modification possible. Ecoinvent 3.2. [22] is used as common background inventory
 79 datasource. The recompiled LCI are compared and the main areas of discrepancy in the battery
 80 modelling are identified. These are pack housing, cell package, battery management system (BMS)
 81 modelling, electrolyte, electrode binder, and energy demand for cell and pack manufacturing plus the
 82 corresponding electricity mix. Very different assumptions and modelling approaches are used for
 83 these components by all considered studies, as can be observed in Table 1. Furthermore, there are
 84 big differences between studies also in the level of detail for modelling the LCI. For example, the LCI
 85 of Zackrisson et al. [18] is comparably simple and based widely on expert judgement or general
 86 assumptions, while Ellingsen et al. [14] provide, especially for the BMS and the battery housing, very
 87 detailed LCI developed together with battery manufacturers.

88 **Table 1.** Overview about the key discrepancies in the LCI between the reviewed studies. * Bauer
 89 models 1 kg of PVdF with 0.5 kg TFE due to the fact that TFE contains twice as much fluor as PVdF.
 90 ** Zackrisson et al. provide two different LCI, one with organic and one with aqueous binder. The
 91 organic binder is based on PVdF (approximated by 50% TFE and 50% PE) and NMP as solvent, while
 92 the aqueous binder is styrene butadiene latex (SBL) in the anode and styrene acrylate latex (SAL) in
 93 the cathode, with SAL being approximated by polymethyl methacrylate and polystyrene in equal
 94 proportions, and SBL by acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ecoinvent datasets). *** NMP is assumed as
 95 solvent, but not balanced in the LCI; i.e. a 100% internal recovery without any NMP makeup is
 96 assumed, why no NMP input or emissions are considered

97

Item	Parameter	Bauer[20]	M-B[21]	Notter[19]	Zack[18]	Eil[14]
Cell chemistry	Type	LTO , NCA	LFP, NCM	LMO	LFP	NCM
Cell container	Type	pouch	can (18650)	pouch	pouch	pouch
	Share of total cell mass	1.5%	25.0%	8.5%	1.3%	0.7%
	Share of total battery mass	1.1%	20.0%	6.8%	1.1%	0.4%
	Package material	PP-UP-Al compound	aluminum	PE foil	PP-Al compound	PET-PA-Al compound, incl. tabs
Pack housing	Share of total battery mass	20.0%	17.0%	14.5%	9.5%	32.0%
	Dominating material	PP	PET	steel	PP	aluminum
BMS	Share of total battery mass	5.0%	3.0%	5.6%	6.0%	3.7%
	Main components	electronics for control unit	copper, chrome steel, integr. circ.	cables, pr. wiring board	transistor, resistor	complex
Cooling system	Share of total battery mass	--	--	--	--	4.10%

Electrolyte	Share of total battery mass	13.9%	12.0%	13.6%	16.5%	9.5%
	Solvent	chemicals, organic	chemicals, organic	ethylene carbonate	ethylene glycol dimethyl ether	ethylene carbonate
	Salt	NaBF ₄	chemicals, inorg.	LiPF ₆	LiCl	LiPF ₆
Binder	Share of total battery mass (cathode & anode)	0.7%	2.38% (LFP) 2.33% (NCM)	0.9%	4.3% (org) 3.6% (aqu)	1.32%
	Type of binder (anode)	TFE 50% *	TFE	Latex	TFE-PE (org) , ABS (aqu) **	PVF
	Type of binder (cathode)	TFE 50% *	TFE	Latex	TFE-PE (org) , ABS (aqu) **	CMC-PAA
	Type of solvent	NMP***	NMP	Water	NMP(org)*** water (aqu)	NMP
Manufact. Energy (cell & pack prod.)	Electricity mix	Japan	UCTE	CN / UCTE	n/a	own mix
	Electricity (kWh/kg)	8.25 (NCA) 9.35 (LTO)	7.5	0.19	11.70	16.80
	Heat (MJ/kg)	27.73 (NCA) 35.78 (LTO)	24.9	0.05	31.68	0.00
	Energy demand (MJ/kg)	57.4 (NCA) 69.5 (LTO)	51.9	0.70	73.80	60.48
	Package and BMS weight	Share (weight) of non-active parts	26.1%	40.0%	26.9%	16.6%

98

99 The recompiled inventory data (LCI) are implemented in openLCA and then restructured / subdivided
100 into components (anode, cathode, housing, etc.), following a common uniform structure. This is
101 necessary for the following parametrization and for contribution analysis on component level,
102 especially for works that provide only aggregated LCI. The previously identified key assumptions are
103 then parametrized, so that they can be varied uniformly for all battery models without altering the rest
104 of the LCI data. The complete recompiled LCI data are provided in the Online Supplementary
105 Information (SI) for direct import into openLCA (ILCD format).

106 2.2 Unification of inventories

107 Considering the identified discrepancies between the studies, it can be concluded that a common
108 base for the varying assumptions is required for increased comparability. For this purpose, the
109 recompiled inventories are modularized, what allows using identical inventories for the previously
110 identified common battery components. For each of the components, the LCI provided by the original
111 studies are compared and the most detailed and comprehensive one is taken as common base and
112 implemented in the new, recompiled LCI. The corresponding values and LCI datasources are listed in
113 Table 2, while the complete modularized inventories are provided in the SI for direct import into
114 openLCA (ILCD format). For the common base, a pouch type cell is assumed, based on the work by
115 Ellingsen et al. [14], who provide the most comprehensive inventory for a pouch cell package. The
116 pack housing is made from polypropylene, with the LCI based on the work of Bauer [20], since plastic
117 is considered to be the material of choice under economic aspects. This is a certain simplification,
118 since the pack housing can also be influenced by the chosen cell chemistry. NCA cells are more
119 problematic under safety aspects than LFP cells, why a plastic housing can be considered more
120 probable for the latter. The corresponding uncertainty has to be taken into account. Still, the overall
121 aim is comparing different battery chemistries with a maximum amount of common parts, while the
122 modular approach allows for easy adaptation of the inventories to other battery pack configurations.
123 For the BMS, very different models are used by the underlying studies. It is assumed that the general

124 composition of a BMS would not differ substantially between battery chemistry. Thus, the inventory
 125 data by Ellingsen et al. is used for all LIB, being the most rigorous model of a BMS available. For the
 126 electrolyte, the situation is similar. All underlying studies assume the electrolyte to be LiPF₆ in an
 127 organic solvent, but use very different proxies for modelling it (see Table 1). Therefore, a unification of
 128 the electrolyte LCI would not alter the battery model at all, but simply use the best proxy for all LIB
 129 types. The corresponding LCI data are taken from Notter et al. [19], who provide the most detailed
 130 modelling of the electrolyte production process. The amount of electrolyte is not altered, since this
 131 would be more than just a unification of common components; it would mean a completely new battery
 132 layout. For the binder, a hybrid approach is used, with a water based binder assumed for the anode,
 133 while for the cathode an organic solvent is used, according to the current state-of-the art [23–25].
 134 Existing studies model either all-organic or all-water based binders, but the use of water-based binder
 135 on the cathode side is considered still as a challenge [26,27]. For the organic binder of the cathode,
 136 the LCI from Bauer [20] is used. As mentioned, a detailed LCI for organic binder is still lacking, why a
 137 dedicated study on electrode binder would be very desirable for reducing the associated uncertainties.
 138 For the water based binder, none of the recompiled studies models carboxy-methyl-cellulose /
 139 styrene-butadiene-rubber (CMC-SBR), the most common water based electrode binder [24,28].
 140 Therefore, the inventory from a third study about sodium-ion batteries is used here [29]. Regarding the
 141 energy demand for battery cell and pack manufacturing, the average value calculated from all studies
 142 is used. While there might be minor differences between battery chemistries, these are neglected,
 143 since the manufacturing energy demand is driven majorly by the production line, especially the dry
 144 room and conditioning facilities [14,15], which are similar for all types of LIB. It can certainly be
 145 discussed if the (extremely low) value used by Notter et al. [19] should be included for calculating the
 146 average energy demand or if better a median value would be used. Still, too few first hand values are
 147 available as to consider it an outlier. Excluding the study of Notter et al. for calculating the average
 148 would increase the value for the manufacturing energy demand by around 20%. However, the
 149 important aspect for this study is the use of a common value for all different battery chemistries, and
 150 due to the parametrised approach other values can easily be used when available in the future (e.g.
 151 first hand industry data). Apart from the amount of energy accounted for, also the electricity mix varies
 152 and thus the associated impacts. While the average chinese electricity shows a comparable high
 153 share of coal based electricity (high impacts), the Japanese mix is significantly cleaner, what further
 154 increases the discrepancies between the studies. Using the same electricity mix (EU mix, with an
 155 average carbon intensity between the Chinese and the Japanese one) therefore further increases the
 156 comparability between the results. However, it has to be taken into account that different parts of a
 157 battery might be manufactured in different locations, and considering the individual electricity mix in
 158 each manufacturing stage would increase the quality of the results. Based on the unified inventories,
 159 this could be done for all battery chemistries similarly, generating detailed disaggregated inventory
 160 data representing the actual market mix while maintaining comparability. The values used for the
 161 common parameters are resumed in Table 2.

162 **Table 2.** Unified assumptions for the common components of the studies (common base).

Item	Parameter	Value	Source
Pack housing	Share of total battery mass	18.6%	average from all studies

	Dominating material	PP	Bauer [20]
Cell package	Type	pouch	
	Share of total cell mass	3.0%	average from all studies that assume pouch cells
	Share of total battery mass	2.4%	average from all studies that assume pouch cells
	Package material	PET-PA-Al foil + Cu/Al tabs	Ellingsen [14]
BMS	Share of total battery mass	4.7%	average from all studies
	Main components		Ellingsen [14]
Cooling system	Share of total battery mass	--	disregarded
Electrolyte	Share of total battery mass	individual	original LCI (unchanged)
	Solvent	Ethylene carbonate	Notter [19]
	Salt	LiPF ₆	Notter [19]
Binder	Share of total battery mass (cathode and anode)	individual	original LCI (unchanged)
	Type of binder (anode)	CMC-SBR	Peters [29]
	Type of binder (cathode)	50% TFE, 50% PE	Bauer [20]
	Type of solvent (anode)	Water	Peters [29],
	Type of solvent (cathode)	NMP	Bauer [20]
Manuf Energy	Electricity mix	EU w/o CH	Ecoinvent [22]
	Electricity (kWh/kg)	9.0	average from all studies
	Heat (MJ/kg)	20.0	average from all studies
	Energy demand (MJ/kg)	52.3	calculated
Package and BMS weight	Share (weight) of non-active parts	25.6%	calculated

163

164 With the unified LCI, also the composition of the battery pack gets altered, i.e. of the amount of non-
 165 active components like package, housing, etc., which make up between 16 and 40% of the final
 166 battery pack mass in the original LCI. This affects the energy density of the battery packs and thus the
 167 results per kWh of storage capacity. The change in pack energy density in comparison to the original
 168 studies is displayed in Table 3.

169 **Table 3.** Comparison of the energy densities (Wh/kg) of the battery packs before and after unification
 170 of the LCI

Energy density (Wh/kg)	M-B (LFP)	Zack (LFP)	Bauer (LTO)	Notter (LMO)	Bauer (NCA)	EII (NCM)	M-B (NCM)
original LCI	88.0	93.0	51.9	114.0	132.3	105.1	112.0
new LCI	109.3	82.9	52.4	116.1	133.1	130.3	139.1

171

172 3 Results

173 3.1 Influence of inventory discrepancies on impacts of battery components

174 In order to provide an idea of the potential influence of the different modelling approaches, the impacts
 175 associated with the production of 1 kg of each of the previously identified battery components subject
 176 to unification are calculated. For impact assessment, the methods recommended by the ILCD are
 177 used [30]. For simplicity purpose, only five categories are discussed in detail: global warming potential
 178 (GWP), acidification potential (AP), human toxicity potential (HTP), particulate matter formation /
 179 respiratory inorganics (PMF), and photochemical ozone formation (POF). These categories have been
 180 identified to be among the most relevant ones for assessing LIB [9]. Resource depletion, while an
 181 issue of significant concern in the field of LCA of batteries and electric mobility, is not discussed further

182 due to the strong dependency of the outcomes on the selected impact assessment methodology
 183 (resource depletion impacts vary fundamentally with the different established LCIA methodologies
 184 [31]). The obtained results are presented in Figure 1. Tabulated results for more impact categories
 185 can be found in the SI. The calculated impacts refer to 1 kg of the corresponding battery component, and
 186 do not reflect the different mass shares that the studies assume for each component, which is another
 187 source of discrepancy.

188

189

190 **Figure 1.** Comparison of the impacts caused by the production of 1 kg of battery component as
 191 modelled by the different studies. M-B = Majeau-Bettez et al., Zack = Zackrisson et al., Elling =
 192 Ellingsen et al.; aqu = aqueous binder, org = organic binder

193 For the **cell container**, the model by Majeau-Bettez et al. shows the highest impacts in the categories
 194 GWP, PMF and POF. The cell container modelled by them is an 18650 cylindrical cell can made
 195 completely of aluminium, whose production is associated with high impacts in these categories. The

196 other cell containers are pouch cells that consist at least partially of plastic material, reducing impacts
197 proportionally. Notter et al. assume a metal-free foil pouch cell made completely of PE, what gives the
198 best results (lowest potential impacts) in all assessed categories. The high impacts obtained by
199 Ellingsen et al. for HTP and AP are basically due to the use of copper for the negative electrode tab of
200 the pouch cell (copper mining is associated with high AP and HTP impacts). The electrode tabs are
201 not modelled by the other studies, why they obtain more favourable results in these categories.

202 For the **pack housing**, the impact of the material choice is clearly visible as well. Comparable results
203 are obtained by the studies that assume plastic housings, while the complexly modelled housing by
204 Ellingsen et al. show significantly higher impacts in all assessed categories, mainly due to the use of
205 aluminium as basic material for the housing, and due to the copper parts (electrode tabs, which are
206 considered to be part of the housing by them). Notter et al. use steel as material, what gives
207 favourable results under GWP and FDP aspects, but higher toxicity impacts in comparison to
208 aluminium.

209 The variation in impacts associated with the **BMS** is attributable to the different modelling of the
210 electronics parts. Ecoinvent provides numerous inventory datasets for electronic components, which
211 vary significantly regarding their composition and thus the corresponding impacts. Majeau-Bettez et al.
212 consider a BMS composition of 50% chromium steel (housing), 40% copper (cables) and 10%
213 integrated circuit, with the production of the latter being energy intensive and requiring notable
214 amounts of precious metals (gold), what drives up the impacts in the categories GWP, HTP, AP and
215 PMF. Zackrisson et al. do not model the BMS as separate module, but associate a certain amount of
216 resistor and transistor to every battery cell, what leads to a high share of these components and thus
217 high requirements of precious metals, leading to high impacts in all categories. The BMS by Bauer,
218 Notter et al. and Ellingsen et al., though modelled very differently, show comparable impacts. The
219 most comprehensive and complex LCI for the BMS is provided by Ellingsen et al., which causes
220 average impacts except for HTP, where the lowest impact is obtained. The ecoinvent process
221 "electronics for control units", used by Bauer, seems to be a realistic, but simple proxy for the BMS,
222 giving, on a mass basis, comparable impacts.

223 Also for the **Electrolyte** very different modelling approaches can be observed. All studies assume the
224 electrolyte to be LiPF_6 salt in an organic solvent, either ethylenecarbonate (EC) or dimethylcarbonate
225 (DMC). Nevertheless, the modelling of these substances differs strongly. Notter et al. and Ellingsen et
226 al. provide the most representative LCIs, both using EC and LiPF_6 , with slightly different shares and
227 from different origin, what causes the different impacts obtained for them. Zackrisson et al. use LiCl as
228 proxy for the lithium salt, whose production is associated with lower impacts than that of LiPF_6 . The
229 remaining studies use generic proxies for solvent and salts ('chemicals, organic', and 'chemicals,
230 anorganic') and can therefore be considered less reliable.

231 Regarding the **Binder**, a clear differentiation between organic solvent based binder (Bauer, Majeau-
232 Bettez et al., Zackrisson et al. (organic) and Ellingsen et al.), and water based binder (Notter et al.,
233 Zackrisson et al. (aqueous)) can be observed, with the water based binders showing significantly lower
234 impacts in all assessed categories. Zackrisson et al. provide two LCI, one for water based binder
235 (SAL) and one organic (PVdF-based). A more detailed breakdown of the impacts associated with the

236 different binder models can be found in the SI. The impacts calculated for the binder include the
237 production of the binder itself, but also the required solvent. In general, high uncertainty is associated
238 with the modelling of the electrode binder. PVdF is the most commonly used organic binder, but a
239 corresponding LCI dataset is available neither in ecoinvent nor in literature. Thus, proxies are used by
240 the studies, either TFE (Majeau-Bettez et al., Bauer), TFE in combination with PE (Zackrisson et al.
241 (organic)), or PVF (Ellingsen et al.). The production of TFE shows extraordinarily high GHG emissions,
242 while those of PVF are lower, but show higher impacts in the remaining assessed categories (Figure
243 1). The choice of the binder proxy therefore has high influence on the GWP results for the battery.
244 Another relevant factor is the solvent production. NMP is assumed by all studies as organic solvent,
245 but the amount required per kg of binder / per kg of electrode paste varies fundamentally. Zackrisson
246 et al. and Bauer do not account for NMP make-up, i.e., they assume (extremely optimistic) 100%
247 internal recovery or simply disregard solvent demand, but also do not consider the potential impacts /
248 increased energy demand associated with solvent recovery. In comparison, Majeau-Bettez et al. and
249 Ellingsen et al. consider that all NMP solvent is evaporated to the atmosphere and has to be added
250 continuously (no internal recovery). The latter drives the environmental impacts up, especially for AP,
251 HTP, PMF and POF, where the production of NMP causes significant impacts, while the production of
252 the binder (TFE or PVF) itself is much less relevant in these categories. Both assumptions can be
253 considered little realistic; an industrial process would recover the major share of the solvent, while not
254 100%, and thus require a certain amount of solvent make-up [29]. All reviewed LCI have some
255 important insufficiencies and a more detailed study and LCI modelling would be helpful to remove
256 doubts about PVdF production impacts and give a final conclusion. Still, it can be deduced that water
257 based binders will most probably be favourable in any case, as far as only little additional efforts are
258 necessary for the changed drying process.

259 The **manufacturing energy** (heat and electricity) required during battery cell and pack production
260 varies up to an order of magnitude between studies. Ellingsen et al., who explicitly focus on the
261 manufacturing energy in their study and use first hand industry data, provide a range of values for
262 different capacity factors in the production plant. As base case for their LCA, they use the lower bound
263 value of this range, assuming a plant at full capacity to be the most realistic assumption. In spite of
264 that, their value still is the highest one among the reviewed studies. While in general the studies all
265 provide values in the same order of magnitude, the study by Notter et al. assumes very low energy
266 demand for manufacturing (about an order of magnitude lower) and therefore looks like an outlier in
267 this sense. The relatively high impacts obtained by Ellingsen et al. for AP and PMF are due to the fact
268 that they assume only electricity as energy input, while all other studies also include a certain share of
269 natural gas as heat source. Compared to natural gas, electricity is associated with higher impacts in
270 AP and PMF, basically due to the share of coal based electricity.

271 When looking at the influence that different modelling assumptions have on the impact of selected
272 battery components, the benefit of a common assessment basis becomes evident. Components that
273 are not depending on the battery chemistry itself but rather on the system configuration should be
274 modelled similarly when battery chemistries want to be compared. In this way, the identified
275 discrepancies (which can be up to an order of magnitude; see Figure 1) are reduced and the
276 significance of the comparison is increased correspondingly.

277 3.2 Influence of inventory unification on LCA results

278 In order to evaluate the effect of the unification of the LCI, the environmental impacts associated with
 279 the production of 1 kg of battery and of 1 kWh of storage capacity are calculated for the original LCI
 280 and then for the new LCI. The results obtained with the new LCI are then contrasted with the findings
 281 from the original studies, visualizing the importance of a comparison based on common assumptions.
 282 The results are given in Figure 2. The two different functional units (FU; 1 kg and 1 kWh) are used
 283 because the LCI unification has two effects: (i) An adjustment of the impacts caused by the production
 284 of a certain amount of battery (mass-related) and (ii) a change in specific energy density due to the
 285 modified share of non-active parts of the battery packs (affecting energy density; see Table 3). Again,
 286 the ILCD impact assessment method is used and the discussion limited to the five categories global
 287 warming potential (GWP), acidification potential (AP), human toxicity potential (HTP), particulate
 288 matter formation / respiratory inorganics (PMF), and photochemical ozone formation (POF).
 289 Information regarding the results for all impact categories are provided in the SI.

290
 291 **Figure 2.** Environmental impacts obtained for the battery models from the different studies, original
 292 LCI (left) and unified LCI (right), per kg of battery (upper row) and per kWh of storage capacity (below)
 293 The environmental impacts obtained with the new LCI change significantly in comparison to the
 294 original ones, especially for GWP and HTP. This visualizes the effect of the discrepancies in
 295 assumptions in the original LCI and points out the importance of using a common base of assumptions
 296 when comparing results from different LCA studies. **Per kg of battery** produced (upper two diagrams
 297 in Figure 2), the GWP impacts are now in a very narrow range, and also for HTP, the variation
 298 between battery chemistries is reduced. For the remaining assessed categories (AP; PMF and POF),

299 the differences and thus the impact of the unification of the LCI is notable, but comparably small. After
300 unification, the LFP-LTO battery is the one that scores best in all assessed categories, except GWP,
301 where LMO-C shows a marginally better result. A ranking of battery chemistries can thus be derived,
302 with LFP-LTO giving the best results, followed by LFP-C and LMO-C (with slightly higher impacts for
303 PMF and HTP), and finally the NCM and NCA based batteries. The latter two show, basically due to
304 the need for nickel and cobalt, significantly higher impacts for AP, PMF, and slightly higher values also
305 for HTP and POF. A distinction between NCM and NCA type batteries can be observed for AP, PMF
306 and POF, where the latter obtains the highest impacts, significantly above that of NCM. This is less
307 due to the different composition of the cathode material than due to the modelling of the NCA active
308 material by Bauer, who assumes significant emissions of NO₂ during the NCA material synthesis
309 process, what leads to very high impacts in this category, as discussed in detail in Chapter 4.

310 On an energy density basis (**per kWh of storage capacity**), the picture changes due to the different
311 energy densities of the battery chemistries. The low energy density of LFP-LTO is reflected by the
312 high relative GHG emissions per kWh of storage capacity, while in the other categories, it is still within
313 the range given by the other LIB types. For some of the batteries, the specific energy density changes
314 significantly (for the LFP by Majeau-Bettez et al. and the NCM by Ellingsen et al., it increases by
315 almost ¼; see Table 3), what affects the final results on an energy basis correspondingly. The GHG
316 emissions per kWh of storage capacity are now inversely proportional to the energy densities, with the
317 high energy battery types (NCA and NCM) obtaining the best results. For AP, PMF and POF, the
318 LMO-C battery gains terrain and is now on the same level as the LFP-C type batteries. Interestingly,
319 the impacts obtained per Wh of storage capacity for HTP are now very close and almost identical for
320 all battery types, except LMO-C, which shows around 25% higher impacts. When looking at all
321 categories jointly, LFP-C type batteries seem to be the most promising ones, with relatively good
322 results in all assessed categories and only slightly elevated GHG emissions per kWh of storage
323 capacity.

324 **4 Discussion**

325 In order to assess the influence of the different assumptions not only for the components in isolated
326 form, but also their impact on the whole battery, a contribution analysis is done. This also helps to
327 identify the effect of the unification of the individual battery components (BMS; package, etc.) on the
328 final results. Figure 3 displays the relative contribution of the main battery components to the total
329 GWP impact obtained for each battery type.

330

331 **Figure 3.** Contribution of main battery components to total GWP impact of each battery (FU = 1 kg of
 332 battery) with unified LCI data. See Table 2 for the underlying common assumptions.

333 As mentioned previously, for **GWP** and on a mass basis (1 kg of battery produced), the impacts
 334 associated with battery production are now, after unification, quite similar between battery chemistries.
 335 This could be expected, since the main drivers for GWP are the energy required for battery
 336 manufacturing (electricity and heat, together responsible for roughly 40% of GWP in average), the
 337 TFE production for the organic binder, but also (to a lower share) the BMS, which all are unified. All
 338 these components are modelled in very different ways by the original studies, and a common LCI base
 339 reduces these differences significantly. The common LCI components package, BMS and energy
 340 demand are responsible for 50-60% of the total GWP impacts.

341 Nevertheless, when looking at the contribution of the individual components, important discrepancies
 342 can be observed. Especially for the cathode, very different pictures are obtained, mainly due to the
 343 different mass shares of cathode current collector and cathode active material assumed by the
 344 studies. For the cathode, the TFE binder shows high GWP impacts. While the type of the binder and
 345 its LCI is unified, the amount of binder remains unchanged, and the different studies assume varying
 346 amounts of binder. Per kg of cathode paste, Majeau-Bettez et al. [21] assume almost 10x the amount
 347 that Notter et al. [19] account for, driving up the corresponding GWP impacts. In contrast, Notter et al.
 348 and Bauer [20], who account for low amounts of binder, calculate with higher share of aluminum in the
 349 cathode (for current collectors, and, in case of NCA, also for the active material). Being aluminum
 350 production highly GHG intensive, this compensates partially for the lower GWP impacts due to the
 351 lower amounts of binder. Unifying the amounts of binder and current collector used for the electrodes
 352 would therefore be of high interest under GWP aspects. On the other hand, for a binder with lower
 353 GWP impacts (e.g. water based; see Figure 1), these discrepancies would have a lower impact on the
 354 final GWP results. Notable is also the relatively high contribution of the binder in the study by Notter et
 355 al. (for all other studies, it is negligible). This is a result of the more complex modelling by Notter et.al,
 356 who assume the separator to contain PVdF, a fluorinated polymer whose production is associated with
 357 significant emissions of GHG, increasing thus the GWP impact of the separator. The other studies use
 358 plain polyethylene film as proxy, associated with low environmental impacts.

359 Considering the relevance of the binder for the GWP impacts, a detailed LCI for PVdF production
 360 would be highly desirable in order to reduce the uncertainties due to the use of inappropriate proxies.
 361 Still, by using the same proxy for all battery types, at least all battery types are affected in the same
 362 way by the underlying uncertainty, increasing comparability.

363 While GWP impacts are relatively similar for all battery types after unification of the LCI, this is not the
 364 case for the remaining impact categories. Here, results vary significantly between batteries. To
 365 support a deeper understanding of the results, Figure 4 displays the contribution of the battery
 366 components relative to the total impact obtained for each battery (normalized to 100%). Otherwise, the
 367 contribution of components would be difficult to read for the battery types with lower impacts. The
 368 different contributions of the unified components (BMS, package, but also manufacturing energy) is a
 369 result of this kind of presentation; for batteries with lower total impact the contribution of these
 370 components is relatively higher (while their absolute impact is identical).

371

372

373 **Figure 4.** Relative contribution of main battery components to total impact of each battery for the
 374 categories acidification (AP), human toxicity potential (HTP), particulate matter formation (PMF), and
 375 photochemical ozone formation (POF). (FU = 1 kg of battery)

376 The impacts for **AP** are driven majorly by the nickel and cobalt mining (nickel and cobalt sulfate
 377 production) as precursor for cathode active material (NCA, NCM). Hence, a clear distinction between
 378 the LFP based battery types and the NCM / NCA ones can be observed, driven by the higher impact
 379 caused by the cathode active material (nickel and cobalt demand). Among the LFP type batteries, only
 380 the one by Zackrisson et al. [18] obtains high AP impacts also for the cathode, with a contribution from
 381 the cathode significantly higher than other LFP type batteries. This is basically due to the emission of
 382 significant amounts of ammonia from the LFP active material synthesis step, what can be considered

383 an overestimation due to the direct use of laboratory data. An industrial process would not emit these
384 amounts of ammonia directly to the atmosphere. Similarly, the high impact obtained by Bauer [20] for
385 the cathode production is mainly a result of the direct nitrogen dioxide emissions assumed by him for
386 the NCA active material production. These cause the very unfavourable results for the NCA-C battery,
387 but would probably not be present in this extent in an industrial process. Another, although smaller
388 factor for the high impact from the NCA cathode by Bauer is the use of a different material proxy for
389 the precursor for active material synthesis. Bauer accounts for pure nickel as NCA precursor, while the
390 other studies assume nickel sulphate in comparable amounts. Naturally, the production of pure
391 metallic nickel shows higher impacts than nickel sulphate. The production of aluminium and copper for
392 current collectors and other parts of the battery is another important contributor and main driver for the
393 impacts caused by the anode. In consequence, the studies that use proportionally high shares of
394 copper current collector (Notter et al. [19], Ellingsen et al. [14] and Majeau-Bettez et al. [21]) show a
395 relatively high contribution from the anode. Furthermore, with the assumed electricity mix, the energy
396 demand for manufacturing contributes another relevant share (between 10 and 30%), mainly due to
397 $\text{SO}_2 / \text{NO}_x$ emissions from coal power plants.

398 For **HTP** impacts, copper mining is the main single driver, i.e. the anode current collectors and cables
399 and current collectors in the BMS, followed by precious metals for electronic components and
400 aluminium. The required copper is responsible for over 50% of the total impacts for all battery types
401 except the LFP-LTO battery and the LFP-C battery by Zackrisson et al. [18]. Thus, the final HTP
402 impacts correlate with the amount of copper assumed for the cathode. Ellingsen et al, who calculate
403 with around 57% of copper in the anode, obtain the highest HTP impact, followed by Notter et al (50%)
404 and Bauer (NCA only; 42%). In contrast, the use of aluminium instead of copper as anode current
405 collector in the LFP-LTO battery significantly reduces the corresponding HTP impacts, making this
406 battery type the most favourable one under HTP aspects. Low impacts are obtained also for the LFP-
407 C by Zackrisson et al., who calculate with an about 3x lower mass of copper for the anode current
408 collector than the other studies (Zackrisson et al. calculate the anode to consist to 20% of copper and
409 80% of active material). However, Zackrisson et al. use 'ferrite (FeMn) for cathode tube production'
410 from the ecoinvent database as iron precursor material for the LFP cathode material, whose
411 production is associated with significant HTP impacts. This increases the impacts from the cathode in
412 comparison with the other LFP-C type battery based on the LCI of Majeau-Bettez et al. [21], who use
413 the ecoinvent dataset for iron sulfate (a waste product, practically free of burden) as a precursor for
414 the LFP synthesis. The former probably overestimates, the latter probably underestimates the
415 associated environmental burdens. Hence, the contribution of components to the total HTP impacts
416 are very different between the different studies, even if the final HTP results are similar. On the other
417 hand, the choice of the cathode active material has comparably low influence on the HTP impacts.

418 The profiles obtained for particular matter formation and respiratory inorganics (**PMF**) is similar to that
419 of AP. Potential impacts are caused majorly by nickel, copper and aluminium production and mining,
420 but also by the generation of the electricity required during cell and battery pack manufacturing. Thus,
421 higher impacts are obtained for the nickel containing chemistries NCA and NCM. The increased
422 impact obtained for the cathode by Zackrisson et al. due to the direct emissions of ammonia from the
423 LFP synthesis process is compensated partially by the lower amount of copper assumed for the anode

424 current collector, so that similar results are obtained for both LFP batteries. Again, the highest impacts
425 are obtained for the NCA battery by Bauer due to the direct nitrogen dioxide emissions from active
426 material production.

427 For photochemical ozone formation (**POF**), very high impacts are obtained for the NCA-type battery.
428 The direct NO₂ emissions from the NCA active material synthesis (Bauer) contribute heavily to the
429 total POF, making cathode production the dominating process and driving up the POF impacts of this
430 battery seriously. Apart from that, the high contributions from the cathode for the nickel containing
431 batteries, NCM and NCA (for the latter masked partially by the high impacts due to the direct NO₂
432 emissions) are a result of the nickel sulphate, and, to a lower extent, also the cobalt sulphate
433 production for the active material. Copper and aluminum production are other sensitive upstream
434 processes, and thus the impacts from cathode and anode correlate with the amount of current
435 collector assumed by the different studies. Minor, but still relevant contributors are the coke production
436 as precursor for the synthetic graphite (anode active material), and titanium dioxide production
437 (relevant only for the LFP-LTO battery as precursor for anode active material).

438 **5 Conclusions**

439 The differences in key assumptions made in existing studies on the environmental impact of Li-Ion
440 battery production are found to be significant. Especially those for estimating the energy demand for
441 cell production vary up to an order of magnitude and influence the results regarding greenhouse gas
442 emissions substantially. In fact, for some of the assessed categories a major share of discrepancies
443 between the studies is due to different assumptions, and less attributable to the particular cell
444 chemistry. This can be noticed especially for the categories global warming and human toxicity, with
445 the former being the most frequently assessed category. Putting the existing LCA studies on a
446 common base regarding these key assumptions therefore provides an improved comparability and
447 allows an improved technology benchmarking of different Li-Ion battery chemistries under
448 environmental aspects. It also facilitates the prospective assessment of future post-lithium or
449 advanced lithium batteries in comparison to existing LIB by providing unified inventories for common
450 components.

451 The LCA results reveal that on a mass basis (1 kg of battery produced), LFP-type batteries seem to
452 score better than other types in all assessed categories. Even when taking into account their lower
453 energy density (on kWh storage capacity basis), they still outscore the NCM and NCA batteries in four
454 of the five assessed categories (except GWP). Nevertheless, in spite of an increased comparability
455 achieved due to inventory unification, an absolute conclusion in this regard cannot be given. Some
456 general aspects of the battery layout that highly influence the LCA results are still modelled very
457 differently, like for example the mass shares of binder and current collector in the anode and cathode.
458 Furthermore, several fundamental inventory gaps with high sensitivity for the results are likewise
459 identified for the upstream processes. For example, the modelling of the most common organic binder,
460 PVdF, is highly uncertain. No LCI for PVdF production exists and the different studies use different
461 proxies from ecoinvent for this material (mainly TFE and PVF), with fundamentally different impacts.
462 Similarly, the inventories for nickel and cobalt sulphate as adapted from ecoinvent by the different

463 studies are highly uncertain, while having a huge impact on the final outcomes. Providing sound and
464 well funded LCI for these processes would help to further reduce uncertainties. Thus, while the
465 comparability of LCA studies on LIB production is increased significantly by using a common inventory
466 base, there are also some major sources of uncertainty yet unresolved, where future research is
467 required urgently. Otherwise, the robustness of future LCA results of battery storage systems will
468 remain limited.

469

470 **Abbreviations**

471 LCA Life Cycle Assessment

472 LCI Life Cycle Inventory

473 ILCD International Reference Life Cycle Data System

474 LIB Lithium-Ion Battery

475 *Impact categories*

476 GWP Global Warming Potential

477 AP Acidification potential

478 HTP Human Toxicity Potential

479 PMF Particulate matter formation / respiratory inorganics

480 POF Photochemical ozone formation

481 *Materials*

482 Al Aluminum

483 Cu Copper

484 Fe Iron

485 CMC Carboxyl-Methyl-Cellulose

486 SAL Styrene-Acrylate-Latex

487 SBR Styrene-Butadiene-Rubber

488 SBL Styrene-Butadiene-Latex

489 PA Polyamide (Nylon)

490 PE Polyethylene

491 TFE Tetrafluoroethylene

492 PVF Polyvinylfluoride

493 PVdF Polyvinylidenfluoride

494 NMP N-Methyl-Pyrrolidone

495 UP Unsaturated Polyester resin

496 ABS Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene

497 PAA Poly Acrylic Acid

498 *Country codes*

499 CH Switzerland

500 CN China

501 JP Japan

502 UCTE

503 EU European Union

504 *Battery chemistries*

- 505 LFP Lithium-Iron-Phosphate with graphite anode
506 LTO Lithium-Iron-Phosphate with lithium-titanate anode
507 NCM Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Manganese-Oxide with graphite anode
508 NCA Lithium-Nickel-Cobalt-Aluminum-Oxide with graphite anode
509 LMO Lithium-Manganese-Oxide with graphite anode

510

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513

514

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Unification of existing inventories for LCA of Li-Ion batteries

First assessment of different Li-ion batteries on common base

Significantly increased comparability of results due unified inventories

LFP type batteries with potentially better environmental performance than NCM/NCA

Disclosure of complete inventory data for import and re-use in ILCD format

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